

More on the black-tail sheet-web spider *Ostearius melanopygius* (O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1879) in South Africa (Araneae: Linyphiidae)

A.S. Dippenaar-Schoeman¹, C.R. Haddad² & R. Steenkamp³

¹SARChI Chair: Biodiversity Value and Change, University of Venda; ²Department of Zoology and Entomology, University of the Free State;

³SANSA Free State team member and Spider Club of Southern Africa

Abstract: The cosmopolitan black-tail sheet-web Spider *Ostearius melanopygius* was for the first time reported from South Africa in 1984. The species was possibly accidentally introduced to South Africa but is now well established in South Africa where it is found in all nine provinces. Photographs of live specimens are provided with notes on their distribution and conservation status in South Africa as well as agrobiont status.

Key words: agroecosystems, agrobiont behaviour, conservation, geographic distribution, South African National Survey of Arachnida.

INTRODUCTION

The genus *Ostearius* Hull, 1911 is represented by only two species *Ostearius melanopygius* (O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1879), a cosmopolitan species described from New Zealand, and *O. muticus* Gao, Gao & Zhu, 1994 from China (World Spider Catalog, 2023). *Ostearius melanopygius* in the course of time appeared to have a world-wide distribution from some countries in Africa, Europe, Asia, and South America.

Ostearius melanopygius was for the first time reported from a few localities in South Africa by Jocqué (1984). The species has been introduced maybe with imported plant material but is now well established in South Africa where it was recorded from all nine provinces (Fig. 15). As part of the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSA), surveys were undertaken throughout the country and the species was frequently sampled especially in crops. The aim of this paper is to provide more information on the morphology of both sexes based on live specimens, their behaviour, distribution, conservation, and agrobiont status in South Africa.

TAXONOMY

Diagnostic characteristics: Size: TL female and male 3–4 mm. Carapace dark, shiny (Figs 1–3) with faint striae (Fig. 7); eyes in two rows; large and rather closely grouped, with the anterior eyes in a straight and the posterior eyes in a slightly recurved line (Fig. 7); posterior eyes are less than one diameter apart; sternum heart shape, brown (Fig. 6); chelicerae straight and similar in both sexes; with a fang groove with five promarginal teeth; clypeus is lower than the median ocular quadrangle and hardly protruding (Figs 7, 9). Abdomen longer than wide; orange red and shiny with small black area posterior around spinnerets (Figs 5–6, 13). Legs are yellow brown, rather long and slender. Male is slightly smaller than female. Male palp distinguished by the bifid form of the retrolateral tibial apophysis (Fig. 11) and the long, gently curved, rigid embolus (Fig. 12). Female epigyne (Fig. 10).

Figures 9–12. *Ostearius melanopygius*. 9. Female carapace. 10. Epigyne. 11. Tibial apophysis. 12. Male palp. Credit: From Bosmans (2007).

Figures 1–8. The Black-tail sheet-web spider *Ostearius melanopygius*. 2–4. Male. 1, 5–8. Female. Photo credits: Rudi Steenkamp.

Figure 13. *Ostearius melanopygius* female in web in Bloemfontein. Photo credit: Nicolette Josling.

LIFESTYLE

The species makes sheet-webs usually close to the soil surface in a variety of habitats. It is an introduced species, but it seems quite established in South Africa where it was found in all nine provinces (Fig. 15). They were sampled from all the floral biomes in South Africa except the Succulent Karoo Biome (Foord *et al.*, 2011; Haddad *et al.*, 2013). They are known as frequent aeronauts that balloon in order to disperse. It was also recorded from a cave in North West province (Jocqué, 1984; Dippenaar-Schoeman & Myburg, 2009).

In South Africa they were frequently sampled from pitfall traps in agroecosystems and might have been imported with plant material. Nineteen linyphiid species have been sampled from crops and orchards in South Africa (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2013) such as apple, citrus, and pistachio orchards (Haddad & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2006) and crops like cabbage, cotton (Mellett *et al.*, 2006), maize, strawberries, tomatoes, and vineyards. Two of the 19 linyphiid species were recognised as agrobionts, namely the cosmopolitan species *O. melanopygius*, which was abundant on cotton, maize, and pistachio, and *Eperigone fradeorum*, which was abundant in cotton fields. In South African maize, the most abundant linyphiids were *O. melanopygius*, *Agyneta habra*, and *Limoneta sirimoni* (Dippenaar-Schoeman, unpublished report, 1989). In pistachio orchards in the Northern Cape, *O. melanopygius* dominated the ground-dwelling fauna and was dominant in all the orchards sampled, comprising 30% of pitfall specimens and 26% of hand-collected specimens and can be considered a pistachio agrobiont (Haddad & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2006). Adults of both sexes are found throughout the year (Fig. 15).

Figure 14. Numbers and phenology of *Ostearius melanopygius* collected by pitfall trapping in pistachio orchards in the Prieska district, Northern Cape province, from August 2001 to July 2002 (pooled data of three orchards). Grey bars indicate immatures, white bars males, and black bars females. (from Haddad & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2006).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION

South America. Introduced to Canada, Europe, Canary Is. to Egypt and Turkey, South Africa, China, Malaysia, Indonesia, and New Zealand (World Spider Catalog, 2023). New: Namibia (Griffin & Dippenaar-Schoeman (1992); Tanzania (Russell-Smith, 2020); Kenya (Kioko *et al.*, 2021).

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA (Fig. 15)

Eastern Cape: Jeffreys Bay (-34.06, 24.91) [Wiese & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2023]; Peddie (Gibraltar Rock) (-33.19, 27.12). **Free State:** Bloemfontein (-29.11, 26.22); Erfenis Dam Nature Reserve (-28.5, 26.8); Parys (Waterval) (-26.9, 27.45); Viljoenskroon (-27.21, 26.96); Vrede (-27.43; 29.13). **Gauteng:** Abe Bailey Nature Reserve (-26.36, 27.4); Cullinan (Renosterkop) (-25.66, 28.51); Olifantsfontein (-25.96, 28.24); Rietondale Research Station (-25.73, 28.23) [Van den Berg & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 1991]; Springbok Flats: Tuinplaas (-24.56, 28.46), Lodge (-24.53, 28.50). **Mpumalanga:** Bethal (Farm Maleas Estate) (-26.44, 29.46); Delmas (Farm Rietvallei) (26.08, 28.57); Groblersdal Agricultural Research Station (-25.16, 29.39); Loskop Research Station (-25.17, 29.4); Lydenburg (-25.09, 30.46); Marble Hall (-24.96, 29.29); Nelspruit Agricultural College (-25.47, 30.96); Oudestad Research Station (-25.16, 29.39); Verloren Vallei Nature Reserve (-25.53, 30.13). **North West:** Brits (-25.62, 27.77); Hartebeespoort Experimental Farm (-25.6, 27.82); Potchefstroom ARC Experimental Farm (-26.7, 27.09); Wolmaransstad (-27.19, 25.97). **Northern Cape:** Prieska (Green Valley Nuts Estate) (-29.68, 22.74); Prieska (Farm Remhoogte) (-29.52, 23). **Western Cape:** Beaufort West (Farm 394) (-32.96, 23.67); Bontebok National Park (-34.07, 20.45); Clanwilliam (-32.16, 18.89); De Hoop Nature Reserve (-34.45, 20.44); Elsenburg (-33.85, 18.83); Fernkloof Nature Reserve (-34.86, 19.34); Hermanus (Fisherhaven) (-34.47, 19.27); Stellenbosch (-33.93, 18.85); Swellendam (-34.02, 20.42); Worcester (-33.64, 19.47).

Figure 15: Map showing the known distribution of *Ostearius melanopygius* in South Africa.

CONSERVATION STATUS

The species has been sampled from six protected areas in South Africa such as: Bontebok National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2021); Erfenis Dam Nature Reserve (Fourie *et al.*, 2013, Haddad *et al.*, 2015); De Hoop Nature Reserve (Haddad & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2009) and Rust de Winter (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 1999). There is no known threats to the species and is listed as Least Concern.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

We thank Nicolette Josling for sharing the photograph (Fig. 13).

REFERENCES

- BERLAND L. 1932. Voyage de MM. L. Chopard et A Mequignon aux Acorcs. Araignees. *Annales de la Societe entomologique de France* 101: 69–84.
- BOSMANS R. 2007. Contribution to the knowledge of the Linyphiidae of the Maghreb. Part XII. Miscellaneous erigonine genera and additional records (Araneae: Linyphiidae: Erigoninae). *Bulletin & Annales de la Société Entomologique de Belgique* 143: 117–163.
- DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., FOORD S.H., HADDAD C.R. & LE ROUX E. 2021. A checklist of the spiders (Arachnida, Araneae) of the Bontebok National Park in the Western Cape Province, South Africa. *SANSA Newsletter* 38: 13–21. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5947479>.
- DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S. & MYBURGH J.G. 2009. A review of the cave spiders (Arachnida: Araneae) from South Africa. *Transactions of the Royal Society of South Africa* 64(1): 53–61.
- DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., VAN DEN BERG A.M., HADDAD C.R. & LYLE R. 2013. Spiders in South African agroecosystems: A review (Arachnida, Araneae). *Transactions of the Royal Society of South Africa* 68: 57–74.
- DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., VAN DEN BERG A.M. & VAN DEN BERG A. 1999. Spiders in South African cotton fields: Species diversity and abundance (Arachnida: Araneae). *African Plant Protection* 5: 93–103.
- FOORD S.H., DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S. & HADDAD C.R. 2011. The faunistic diversity of spiders (Arachnida, Araneae) of the Savanna Biome in South Africa. *Transactions of the Royal Society of South Africa* 66: 170–201.
- FOURIE R., HADDAD C.R., DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S. & GROBLER A. 2013. Ecology of the plant-dwelling spiders (Arachnida: Araneae) of the Erfenis Dam Nature Reserve, South Africa. *Koedoe* 55(1), 9 pages. doi: 10.4102/koedoe.v55i1.1113.
- GRIFFIN E. & DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S. 1992. A checklist of and references to the Namibian spider fauna (Arachnida, Araneae). *Cimbebasia* 13: 155–181.
- HADDAD C.R. & DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S. 2005. Epigeic spiders (Arachnida: Araneae) in Nama Karoo grassland in the Northern Cape Province. *Navorsinge nasionale Museum, Bloemfontein* 21(1): 1–10.
- HADDAD C.R. & DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S. 2006. Epigeic spiders (Araneae) in pistachio orchards in South Africa. *African Plant Protection* 12: 12–22.
- HADDAD C.R. & DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S. 2009. A checklist of the non-acarine arachnids (Chelicerata: Arachnida) of the De Hoop Nature Reserve, Western Cape Province, South Africa. *Koedoe* 51(1): 1–9.
- HADDAD C.R., DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., FOORD S.H., LOTZ L & LYLE R. 2013. The faunistic diversity of spiders (Arachnida, Araneae) of the Grassland Biome in South Africa. *Transactions of the Royal Society of South Africa* doi:10.1080/0035919X.2013.773267.
- HADDAD C.R., DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S. & PEKÁR S. 2005. Arboreal spiders (Arachnida: Araneae) in pistachio orchards in South Africa. *African Plant Protection* 11: 32–41.
- HADDAD C.R., FOORD S.R., FOURIE R. & DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S. 2015. Effects of a fast-burning spring fire on the ground-dwelling spider assemblages (Arachnida: Araneae) in a central South African grassland habitat. *African Zoology* <http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/15627020.2015.1088400>.
- HADDAD C.R., LOUW S. VD M. & DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S. 2004. Spiders (Araneae) in ground covers of pistachio orchards in South Africa. *African Plant Protection* 10(2): 97–107.
- JOCQUÉ R. 1984. Linyphiidae (Araneae) from South Africa. Part I: The collection of the Plant Protection Research Institute, Pretoria. *Journal of the Entomological Society of South Africa* 47: 121–146.
- KIOKO G.M., MARUSIK Y.M., LI S.Q., KIOKO E.N. & JI L.Q. 2021. Checklist of the spiders (Araneae) of Kenya. *African Invertebrates* 62(1): 49–229 doi:10.3897/AfrInvertebr.62.58776.
- MELLET M.A., SCHOEMAN A.S. & DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S. 2006. Effect of Bt-cotton cultivation on spider (Arachnida: Araneae) populations near Marble Hall, Mpumalanga, South Africa. *African Plant Protection* 12: 40–50.
- RUSSELL-SMITH A. 2020. A checklist of the spiders of Tanzania. *Journal of East African Natural History* 109(1): 1–41.
- VAN DEN BERG A. & DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S. 1991. Ground living spiders from an area where the harvester termite *Hodotermes mossambicus* occurs in South Africa. *Phytophylactica* 23: 247–253.
- WHITEMORE C., SLOTOV S., CROUCH T.E. & DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S. 2001. Checklist of spiders (Araneae) from a savanna ecosystem, Northern Province, South Africa: including a new family record. *Durban Museum Novitates* 26: 10–19.
- WIESE L. & DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S. 2023. SANSA Eastern Cape surveys: A checklist of the spiders (Arachnida, Araneae) of Jeffreys Bay, South Africa. *SANSA Newsletter* 45: 19–28. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7831510>.
- WORLD SPIDER CATALOG. 2023. Version 24.5. Natural History Museum Bern, online at <http://wsc.nmbe.ch>, accessed on August 2023. doi: 10.24436/2.